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Integrating SDGs into the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering

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ABSTRACT

Universities are increasingly re-thinking their role in the twenty-first century and looking to be both more responsive to societal needs and to become agents of change towards solving global challenges. As a universally agreed framework, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide an organising structure for what this looks like for the University.

This paper develops the work undertaken by the Civil Engineering School at Universitat Politècnica de València (Spain) to adapt the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering program curriculum so that SDGs will be integrated into the student outcomes. In fact, one of the targets for the SDGs announced by the United Nations in September 2015 aims to ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development.

Civil engineering is one of the professions that most affects our environment. Indeed, infrastructures modify and shape our world to make better societies, but it is imperative engineers are aware of the consequences their decisions have. In this context, it is of paramount importance that civil engineering programs include one of the most ambitious and important global agreements related with sustainable development.

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To achieve this goal, a diagnosis of the program curriculum was developed to identify at what extent the different subjects and courses are related with the 17 SDGs. Weaknesses and non-related SDGs were identified and minimum requirements defined to be added into the program to achieve the 2030 agenda goals. In addition, a sustainable rubric is proposed, in order to analyse the ability of students to incorporate sustainability principles into their work.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Spanish 2030 Agenda

On September 25th 2015, the General Assembly of the United Nations (UN) adopted one of the most ambitious and transcendent global agreements of our time: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development with the slogan “Transforming our world” [1]. The Agenda is an action plan for people, the planet and prosperity and also seeking to strengthen universal peace in larger freedom.

The Agenda proposes 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with 169 integrated and indivisible targets aiming at addressing the most urgent global challenges: ending poverty and promoting economic prosperity, social inclusion, environmental sustainability, peace and good governance for all peoples by 2030.

In June 2018, the Spanish Government approved the “Action Plan for the 2030 Agenda Implementation” [2]. The document presents the state of the country and analyses the situation of SDGs in Spain as well as the actions to be carried out to implement the Agenda. Within the document, the University is mentioned as a key actor that must commit to the implementation of the Agenda; seven contributions from Spanish universities to the application of the 2030 Agenda are explicitly indicated [2]. Among them, we highlight:

- a) (2) *A firm commitment with the inclusion of outcomes related to a sustainable and inclusive development, both necessary for the construction of a global citizenship; the commitment must involve the training of all students, the teaching and research staff and also the administration and services staff.*
- b) (3) *The generation and transfer of knowledge committed to sustainable development, including knowledge needed to implement and monitor the 2030 Agenda progress.*
- c) (7) *Commitment from the universities to report on impacts in terms of teaching, research and transfer, regarding the implementation of each SDG.*

Within this context, the Vice-Rectorate for Studies, Quality and Accreditation at Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), is carrying out a teaching innovation program to adapt the graduates outcomes with SDGs, by incorporating them into the curriculum learning outcomes. First, students will have to incorporate into their Bachelor Thesis an explicit critical analysis justifying to which extent their work relates to SDGs. In addition, students will have the opportunity to enrol for specialised and specific on-line training on each SDG. In a second stage, the incorporation of SDGs

into the Degree programs will be encouraged, at all levels. The work presented herein focuses on the possibilities for the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering program.

1.2 Civil Engineering and SDGs

In today's societies, professional activity has a significant role and clearly influences the structure and behaviour of our social life. Therefore, it is of paramount importance that professionals know and assume SDGs in their daily tasks to ensure strongly committed societies with the 2030 Agenda.

Civil engineers have a great responsibility as agents that transform the environment; since the creation of the first Institution of Civil Engineers (ICE) in the United Kingdom, civil engineers have reflected on the work they do. In 1828, during the ICE creation, Tredgold [3] defined civil engineering as *“being the art of directing the great sources of power in nature for the use and convenience of man, as the means of production and of traffic in states, both for external and internal trade, as applied in the construction of roads, bridges, aqueducts, canals, river navigation, and docks, for internal intercourse and exchange; and in the construction of ports harbours, moles, breakwaters, and lighthouses, and in the art of navigation by artificial power, for the purposes of commerce; and in the construction and adaptation of machinery, and in the drainage of cities and towns”*. This definition has evolved over time and in 2007 the institution rephrased it: *“civil engineering is a vital art, working with the great sources of power in nature for the wealth and well-being of the whole of society”*.

Civil engineering associations worldwide define civil engineering in similar terms; for example the American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE) of the United States says that *“civil engineers design, build, and maintain the foundation for our modern society – our roads and bridges, drinking water and energy systems, sea ports and airports, and the infrastructure for a cleaner environment”*.

Following the Summit on the Future of Civil Engineering held in June 2006, ASCE published the document "The Vision for Civil Engineering in 2025", which establishes an aspirational global vision of the profession for the 21st century [4]: *“In 2025, civil engineers serve competently, collaboratively, and ethically as master:*

- a) planners, designers, constructors, and operators of society’s economic and social engine—the built environment;*
- b) stewards of the natural environment and its resources;*
- c) innovators and integrators of ideas and technology across the public, private, and academic sectors;*
- d) managers of risk and uncertainty caused by natural events, accidents, and other threats; and*
- e) leaders in discussions and decisions shaping public environmental and infrastructure policy.*

In general, all civil engineering associations in the world adopt these definitions to explain the civil engineer's tasks and their importance in shaping the environment for better societies, for instance, by establishing transportation networks or by ensuring a

sustainable resources' management. All these challenges represent a great responsibility and a direct influence on the achievement of the 2030 Agenda. As a consequence, it is worthy necessary that Schools of Civil Engineering promote and educate students to achieve SDGs during their professional development.

The School of Civil Engineering at UPV, is analysing how to integrate SDGs in the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering program curriculum, to ensure that graduates outcomes incorporate the main challenges of SDGs related to civil engineering.

2 HOW TO START

2.1 Methods

Many universities have incorporated sustainability into their academic programs ([5], [6], [7], [8] and [9]). These experiences are a good starting point to integrate SDGs in the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering program curriculum. Different methodologies are usually used for analysis of academic programs: surveying for students, curriculum detailed analysis, interviews with academic staff or with other actors involved in the graduates' curriculum, etc.

Within this work, we have followed a methodology based on the STAUNCH tool [10] for integrating SDGs into the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering program curriculum. The steps to be achieved are:

- a) Selection of criteria to be analysed.
- b) Information gathering; all program course syllabi are analysed, focusing on objectives, outcomes and assessment methods.
- c) Information classification.
- d) Program analysis and proposals.

For this purpose, it is necessary to identify the SDG-related topics that are already being taught, identifying which SDG target they contribute to. Potential courses that can contribute will also be identified as well as new needed topics. Finally, activities developed in the School will also be analysed from a SDG perspective so that students acquire from a holistic way skills and knowledge that the 2030 Agenda addresses.

The 59 courses within the academic program were analysed (*Table 1*); interviews with academic staff responsible of potential courses to include SGD-oriented topics were also held to receive their input.

Table 1. Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering: program curriculum.

Code	Subject	ECTS	Courses
MAT	Mathematics for civil engineering (CE)	19.5	Mathematical fundamentals of CE Mathematical methods of CE Mathematics - Extension course
MMO	Mathematical modelling	10.5	Basic programming and numerical methods Basic statistics
REP	Representation systems	12.0	Drawing Representation systems
PHY	Physics for CE	19.5	Fundamentals of physics in CE Mechanics Physics- Extension course
ECO	Economics and business	4.5	Economics, legislation and business management
GEO	Geology	6.0	Geology applied to civil works
TOP	Topography and cartography	4.5	Surveying
FBU	Fundamentals of building engineering	25.5	Chemistry for civil engineering Construction materials and their application to CE Construction procedures (I) and (II) Electrical engineering
FST	Fundamentals of structural engineering	21.0	Mechanics of deformable solids Structural analysis Structural concrete / Structural steel (I)
GTC	Geotechnics	6.0	Geotechnics and foundations
HHY	Hydraulics and hydrology	7.5	Hydraulics and hydrology
FEN	Fund. of environ. impact	4.5	Science and environmental impact of CE
BUS	Business management	4.5	Business management
RIN	Road infrastructures	10.5	Highways and airports / Railways
TRA	Transportation and land dev.	4.5	Transportation and land development
BEN	Building engineering	15.0	Industrialized construction Maritime works Risk prevention and work organization
HYD	Hydraulic infrastructures	6.0	Hydraulic infrastructures
BDG	Building	6.0	Building
LAN	Land engineering	6.0	Geotechnical eng. techniques and methods
PRO	Projects	4.5	Projects
COM	Training complements for civil engineering	31.5	Building Information Modelling Civil engineering and society Conceptual design of bridges Concrete structural elements Construction management and organization Ethics in CE Geotechnical design of foundations and ret. walls Hydraulic and energy facilities Infrastructure maintenance management Introduction to water quality Management of construction and consulting Mobility and urban transport Philosophy of structures Port facilities River basin manag., water res. and river eng. Road safety Structural design of foundations and ret. walls Structural steel (II) Surface and groundwater hydrology Technology of concrete structures Urban history and planning Urban hydraulic facilities
THE	Bachelor thesis	12.0	Bachelor thesis

2.2 Diagnosis

Once the program curriculum analysed, we notice that, as expected, the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering has great potential to integrate SDGs into the students' outcomes.

The detailed analysis of the 59 course syllabi (*Table 1*) shows that there are currently only 17 courses explicitly working with any of the 169 targets defined within the 17 SDGs. These 17 courses are directly related to 11 of the 17 SDGs. This means that in 18 of the 22 subjects within the program curriculum, some of the SDGs targets are worked on (*Table 2*).

Table 2. SDG targets developed (green) or with potential to be developed (yellow) within the program curriculum subjects.

Code	SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL																
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
MAT																	
MMO																	
REP																	
PHY																	
ECO					5.5			8.2 8.4 8.8		10.4		12.6					
GEO						6.6							13.3				
TOP																	
FBU			3.9			6.3	7.3		9.4			12.4 12.5					
FST									9.4			12.2					
GTC																	
HHY						6.4			9.4		11.5 11.b	12.2	13.1		15.1		
FEN					5.5	6.6		8.4 8.5			11.3 11.4 11.6		13.3		15.1 15.2 15.3 15.4 15.9		
BUS					5.5			8.3 y 8.8	9.4			12.2 12.6					17.7
RIN									9.1 9.4		11.2	12.2					
TRA			3.6			6.6			9.1 9.4		11.4 11.6 11.7		13.1				
BEN							7.2	8.8	9.4		11.5 11.b	12.2	13.1	14.1 14.2 14.7			
HYD		2.4				6.1 6.2	7.2					12.2	13.1				
BDG											11.1 11.c	12.2					
LAN												12.2					
PRO									9.4		11.b	12.2	13.1 13.3				
COM		2.4	3.6 3.9	4.7	5.5 5.c	6.1 6.2 6.3 6.4 6.5 6.6	7.2	8.3 8.8	9.1 9.2 9.4	10.2	11.1 11.2 11.3 11.4 11.5 11.b	12.2 12.6 12.7 12.8	13.1 13.3	14.1 14.4	15.1	16.7	17.7 17.14 17.17
THE	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

(*) the target will depend on the specific bachelor's thesis topic

The following SDGs must be highlighted:

- a) SDG #6 “Clean water and sanitation” is developed into 6 courses within years 1, 3 and 4.
- b) SDG #9 “Industry, innovation and clean energy” is developed into 4 courses within years 2 and 4.
- c) SDG #11 “Sustainable cities and infrastructure” is developed into 5 courses within years 3 and 4.
- d) SDG #13 “Climate action” is developed into 3 courses within years 3 and 4.

However, this analysis has shown, first, that courses already working with any of the SDGs still have potential to integrate other SDGs. Then, there are 25 courses clearly aligned with some SDGs that although they do not work them at present, they also have potential to do so, as their topics and outcomes are linked to the targets defined within the 17 SDGs. Finally, there are only 17 courses within the program curriculum where there is not an evident link to SDGs; they basically correspond to subjects of basic training in mathematics, physics and drawing.

Given the SDG targets directly related to the previously identified courses, we demonstrate that civil engineering is basically related to 5 of the 17 SDGs. These SDGs are the most related to the program curriculum so the ones with most potential to be developed in many courses within the curriculum are:

- a) SDG #6 “Clean water and sanitation”: up to 10 courses.
- b) SDG #9 “Industry, innovation and clean energy”: up to 25 courses.
- c) SDG #11 “Sustainable cities and infrastructure”: up to 15 courses.
- d) SDG #12 “Responsible production and consumption”: up to 16 courses.
- e) SDG #13 “Climate action”: up to 12 courses.

The rest of SDGs can be integrated in different courses (between 1 and 9) with different depth and scope, depending on the specific case. In addition, all SDGs can be developed within other university activities that lead to ECTS credits recognition foreseen by the Spanish law (Royal Decree RD1393/2007).

Courses with the greatest potential to include SDGs, considering the number of SDGs that are integrated or have potential to, are the following:

- a) Transportation and land development (year 2): 5 SDGs
- b) Hydraulics and hydrology (year 3): 6 SDGs
- c) Maritime works (year 3): 6 SDGs
- d) Business management (year 4): 5 SDGs
- e) Hydraulic infrastructures (year 4): 6 SDGs
- f) Management of construction and consulting (year 4): 5 SDGs
- g) Ethics in civil engineering (year 4): 8 SDGs

The year 4 course “Civil engineering for society” has a relevant importance since it is the only subject of the curriculum linked to SDG# 16 “Peace, justice and strong institutions”. In the same way, the course “Ethics in civil engineering” is the only course that develops SDG# 4. The next section develops a proposal with specific actions.

3 PROPOSAL

3.1 Actions in three levels

Continuous improvement in a degree program at Universitat Politècnica de València includes, according to the Quality Manual of the institution, actions in two areas: improvements in the University's or the School's own processes and improvements in the design of the academic program itself.

Improvements in the program design must be undertaken by the program Academic Committee, which must analyse, assess and incorporate them into the corresponding annual report of the degree. These improvements can lead to two situations:

- a) The improvement proposal does not imply a modification of the program verification. In this case, after the evaluation of the UPV Quality Service, its implementation is immediate and is the responsibility of the school.
- b) The improvement proposal implies a modification of the program verification. In this case, the modification process must be initiated to submit the new title proposal for verification by the National Agency for Quality Evaluation and Accreditation (ANECA). In the Spanish context, this is a long and administratively complicated procedure that can last up to two years.

Within this context, actions are proposed at three different levels to incorporate SDGs into the learning outcomes and professional profile of the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering graduates

The first level, which is immediate to apply, consists of introducing transversal activities related to the 2030 Agenda, so that all students know their extent. The most immediate way of achieving this purpose is by proposing a compulsory training activity for first-year students that can be taught within the framework of the Tutorial Action Program (PATU) [11]. This activity will explain the objectives of the 2030 Agenda, the 17 SDGs and the 169 targets. This level corresponds to the previously mentioned improvements in the own processes, in this case, of the School.

The second level will propose changes at the program subject level. Following the analysis presented in section 2, all subjects related to SDGs are known. Given this, it is proposed to hold meetings with the academic coordinators of courses within these subjects, together with experts in the 2030 Agenda, to address changes to effectively include SDGs into the students' learning outcomes. This level corresponds to improvement proposals that do not imply a modification of the program verification. Consequently, their implementation is relatively simple and viable.

Finally, the third level corresponds to improvement proposals that imply a modification of the program verification. The room for change and the immediacy in the implementation of these proposals is very limited, as previously mentioned. However, it is also important to consider actions at this level, since they are the ones that can lead to more integrated and articulated changes throughout the program curriculum.

All the potential possibilities detected in the diagnosis can be addressed with actions at the second level, given that they would simply include specific actions in the different course syllabi. On the other hand, future revisions of the curriculum that would lead to modifications in the program verification must address if courses at present elective should be compulsory within the program curriculum, for instance, “Civil Engineering for Society” or “Ethics in Civil Engineering”.

3.2 Action efficiency assessment

Besides studying how to introduce SDGs into the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering program curriculum, we also had to consider how to assess that students have achieved these learning outcomes. All students must pass exams to verify that they have reached the learning outcomes, so topics related to SDGs that were introduced in each course are relatively easy to assess (of course, assessment activities must be adequately defined so that this statement is valid). In addition, it is also very important to realise that integration of these contents in the program curriculum will make them present in every work that civil engineers will develop in their professional activity.

Once the students leave the School, it is very difficult to track them from the professional perspective (it will be the responsibility of the professional associations). The last academic chance to assess them regarding at what extent their learning outcomes are aligned with the SDGs is with their Bachelor Thesis. At this point, they will develop the most similar activity to the technical work that they will carry out during their professional career.

Therefore, a rubric (a sustainable holistic rubric) has been developed to analyse the ability of students to incorporate SDGs into their work (*Table 3*). This rubric is based on that presented by Crespo et al. (2017) [12]. The rubric has been designed considering the five parts in which SDGs are grouped and four levels of achievement (A, B, C and D) to assess the integration of SDGs. Two scopes, potential and assigned are considered. The adaptation of the rubric to four levels has been made to maintain the same assessment system that is carried out at UPV to evaluate the generic outcomes.

The potential score will be used to indicate whether the Bachelor Thesis has potential to include some SDGs. In this case, A means “required”; the SDG must be present and its presence is critical for the development of the Bachelor Thesis. B means “adequate”; it is advisable that the SDG is present within the work. C means “valid”; the SDG can be present within the work, although it is not necessary. Finally, D means “not applicable”; the SDG is not linked to the work.

The assigned score shows the development level of each SDG in the Bachelor Thesis. In this case A means “excellent”; there is evidence that the SDG is present in the work, and its inclusion conditioned the final result. B means “adequate”; the SDG is mentioned and applied throughout the work; C means “deficient”; the SDG is

mentioned, but it is not applied or applied in an unclear or incorrect way. Finally D means “failure”; the SDG is not included within the work.

Table 3. The sustainable holistic rubric

Factors to consider	Potential	Assigned
People		
SDG #1 No poverty SDG #2 Zero hunger SDG #3 Good health and well-being SDG #4 Quality education SDG #5 Gender equality		
Planet		
SDG #6 Clean water and sanitation SDG #12 Responsible consumption and production SDG #13 Climate action SDG #14 Life below water SDG #15 Life on land		
Prosperity		
SDG #7 Affordable and clean energy SDG #8 Decent work an economic growth SDG #9 Industry, innovation and infrastructure SDG #10 Reduced inequalities SDG #11 Sustainable cities and communities		
Peace		
SDG #16 Peace, justice and strong institutions		
Partnerships		
SDG #17 Partnerships for the goals		

4 CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering program curriculum taught at Universitat Politècnica de València leads to the following conclusions:

- a) Training of civil engineers must include SDGs into their curriculum.
- b) The revision of the course syllabi within the different subjects of the program curriculum, has led to identify the presence and potential incorporation of the different SDGs into the civil engineers’ training.
- c) Actions at three levels have been considered to incorporate SDGs into the curriculum.
- d) A rubric is proposed to assess the ability of students to incorporate SDGs into their work, at course level and at their Bachelor Thesis.

With all this information, changes will be introduced in the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering program curriculum at UPV and their effectiveness will be assessed. Consequently, all graduates will know the content of the 2030 Agenda, and will be able to take into account SDGs in their future daily professional practice.

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